

ON ORGANO-ARSENICAL COMPOUNDS PART IV

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Some *N*-alkylated acetamidine derivatives containing the arsenious acid group have been synthesised. These amidines show virtual tautomerism and no isomeric forms could be obtained by altering the mode of formation.

In part III of this series of papers (Pathak and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 254) the synthesis of *N*-alkylated acetamidines of the type (I), by condensing *p*-arsanilic acid with acetanilide or its derivative in presence of POCl_3 , has been described. It is, however, possible to visualise two different isomeric formulæ (I and II) for such a symmetrical disubstituted amidine:—

(I)

(II)

It has been therefore considered desirable to see if the isomeric compound (II) can be prepared by altering the order of combination. But, so far no isomeric forms could be isolated as these amidines showed virtual tautomerism (cf. von Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 869, 2362; 1897, 30, 1779; Sen and Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 646; Bures and Kundera, *Chem. Abst.*, 1935, 29, 4750). The following sets of condensations have been carried out in presence of POCl_3 and in each set the same respective compound, which is an acetamidine derivative containing an arsenious acid group, has been isolated without the formation of any isomer: (A) Condensation of *p*-arsanilic acid with acetanilide and that of *p*-acetylaminophenylarsonic acid with aniline, (B) condensation of *p*-arsanilic acid with *p*-chloroacetanilide and that of *p*-acetylaminophenylarsonic acid with *p*-chloroaniline, and (C) condensation of *p*-arsanilic acid with *p*-methoxyacetanilide and that of *p*-acetylaminophenylarsonic acid with *p*-anisidine. In this connection, it is significant to note that the presence of the arsenious acid group has not in any way impaired the mobility of the hydrogen atom.

As shown in part III, all these acetamidine derivatives containing arsenious acid group have been isolated by using POCl_3 as the condensing agent (cf. Hewett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1204) and in no case the expected arsonic acid has been obtained. That all these compounds are arsenious acids and not arsonic acid derivatives has been confirmed by also using *p*-acetylaminophenylarsenoxide (Berthelm, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1073) in place of *p*-acetylaminophenylarsonic acid for the above condensations, when the same respective compounds have been obtained.

In order to investigate whether an acetamidine derivative containing two arsenious acid groups can be synthesised, the condensation of *p*-acetylaminophenylarsonic acid with *p*-arsanilic acid has been studied in presence of POCl_3 , when a compound (m.p. $250-55^\circ$ containing 27.2% As) has been obtained, which could neither be purified nor characterised. Its properties, however, show that it is an arsenious acid derivative and does not contain any arsonic acid group.

The above type of acetamidine derivative containing arsenious acid group is readily reduced to the arseno derivative with hypophosphorus acid in presence of a trace of potassium iodide.

EXPERIMENTAL

(*Phenyl-4-chloro*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I, R=Cl).—(a). *p*-Chloroaniline (5 g.) was slowly added, under cooling, to phosphorus oxychloride (50 c.c.). After the addition was over, well-powdered *p*-acetylaminophenylarsonic acid (10 g.) was gradually added and the mixture was then heated in an oil-bath at $125^\circ-128^\circ$ for about 4 hours. Next day, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, when a pasty mass was obtained. The supernatant liquid was decanted and treated under cooling with excess of ammonium hydroxide, when a solid was precipitated. It was triturated with ammonium hydroxide and then dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution was then acidified, under cooling, with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid, when a minute quantity of a flocculent precipitate was obtained, which was then filtered. The clear acid solution was basified with excess of ammonium hydroxide, when a colorless solid (3 g.) was obtained. It is practically insoluble in hot water and sparingly soluble in alcohol and could not be crystallised from any organic solvent. It was therefore again purified as above. It melts at 155° to a brown, viscous liquid. (Found: N, 7.71; As, 20.84. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{ClAs}$ requires N, 7.95; As, 21.27 per cent.) It is readily soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and in dilute alkali, but insoluble in aqueous ammonia or bicarbonate solutions. Its acetic acid solution readily decolorises iodine solution and it remains unaffected, when its solution in dilute sulphuric acid is saturated with sulphur dioxide in presence of a trace of potassium iodide. From its solution in 10% aqueous caustic soda it is precipitated as such when saturated with sodium chloride.

From the pasty mass, mentioned above, a further quantity (3.2 g.) of the compound (I, R=Cl) was obtained by trituration with 10% caustic soda solution and subsequent treatment of the alkaline solution, as described above.

(b). The condensation of *p*-arsanilic acid with *p*-chloroacetanilide in presence of phosphorus oxychloride has been similarly carried out and the compound, isolated and purified as described above, has been found to be identical in all respects with (I, R=Cl).

(c). The condensation of *p*-acetylaminophenylarsenoxide (prepared by acetylating *p*-aminophenylarsenoxide, following the method of Bertheim, *loc cit.*) with *p*-chloroaniline in presence of phosphorus oxychloride, similarly carried out, has yielded a product found to be identical in all respects with (I, R=Cl).

(*Phenyl*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I, R=H) has been obtained by condensing *p*-acetylamino-phenylarsonic acid with aniline in presence of phosphorus oxychloride; it melts at 146-48° to a viscous mass. In course of this preparation, a small quantity of brownish, arsenic-free compound, soluble in dilute alkali but insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and in ammonium hydroxide, has also been isolated, which, however, could not be purified and characterised.

The above compound (I, R=H) has been found to be identical with the condensation product of *p*-arsanilic acid with acetanilide (as described in part III) and also with the one obtained by condensing *p*-acetylamino-phenylarsenoxide with aniline in presence of POCl₃.

(*Phenyl-4-methoxy*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I, R=OCH₃) has been similarly obtained by condensing *p*-arsanilic acid with *p*-methoxyacetanilide. The colorless solid melts at 156-57° to a brown viscous liquid. (Found: N, 7.65; As, 20.98. C₁₆H₁₇O₃N₂As requires N, 8.04; As, 21.52 per cent). It has been found to be identical with the condensation product of *p*-acetylamino-phenylarsonic acid with *p*-anisidine, and also with the one obtained by condensing *p*-acetylamino-phenylarsenoxide with *p*-anisidine, both in presence of POCl₃.

(*Phenyl-4-nitro*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I, R=NO₂).—(a). This yellow compound (m.p. 175°) has been obtained by condensing *p*-arsanilic acid with *p*-nitroacetanilide in presence of POCl₃. (Found: N, 11.28; As, 20.1. C₁₄H₁₄O₄N₃As requires N, 11.57; As, 20.63 per cent).

(b). The condensation of *p*-nitroaniline with *p*-acetylamino-phenylarsonic acid in presence of POCl₃ has yielded a yellow solid which contains, besides arsenic, chlorine. It could neither be purified nor characterised.

(4 : 4'-*Dimethoxydiphenyl*)-(4 : 4'-*arsenophenyl*)-acetamidine was obtained, as usual, by reduction of a hydrochloric acid solution of (I, R=OMe) with hypophosphorus acid in presence of a trace of potassium iodide. The yellowish solid (insoluble in dilute alkali) darkens at 265° and does not melt even at 300°. (Found: As, 24.46. C₂₀H₂₀O₂N₄As₂ requires As, 23.85 per cent.).

Reduction of (I, R=OMe) with sodium hydrosulphite in presence of magnesium chloride was attempted at 20-25°. The yellowish solid (insoluble in dilute alkali) isolated has been found to contain traces of combined sulphur and does not melt even at 300°. The sulphur containing impurity, however, could not be removed from this impure product.